

LEXICAL AND GRAMMATICAL ANALYSIS OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH PROVERBS

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***Abstract:** Idiomatic idioms, proverbs, and sayings have a strong connection to the history and culture of a particular country. They are therefore not well understood by other countries. This is one of the reasons why some academics argue that certain lexical terms cannot be translated; nevertheless, other writers have suggested several translation approaches to address this issue. This article specifically analyzes this issue. Comparative, contrastive, and content analyses were all used in this study.*

***Keywords:** equivalent of English and Uzbek languages, translated metaphorically and literally, translating techniques of proverbs, untranslatable.*

INTRODUCTION

Proverbs, sayings, and idioms have been referred to as the "miracles of the language" by renowned Uzbek translator Ghaybullas Salomov.

A proverb is "a short, generally understood sentence of the folk that contains wisdom, truth, morals, and traditional views in a metaphorical, fixed, and memorable form and that is handed down from generation to generation," according to Mieder (1985: 119). It begs the question of why the proverbs are in a form that can be memorized. The answer is straightforward: Because they are short and incorporate stylistic devices (metaphor, antithesis, parallelism, alliteration, and rhyme), listeners are more likely to recall, repeat, and learn them.

Research materials

We employed one monolingual Uzbek proverbial dictionary. O‘zbek xalq maqollari [Uzbek people proverbs] were compiled by T. Mirzayev, A. Musoqulov, and B. Sarimsoqov and published in 2005.

The second research material is the Oxford Dictionary of Proverbs (6 ed.), which was compiled by J. Speake and published in 2015. This valuable resource provided explanations, origins, and themes for the proverbs. We used the online dictionary <https://idioms.thefreedictionary.com> along with the Oxford Dictionary of Proverbs to identify the meanings of proverbs in the original text.

1. Time is money—Vaqt pul demakdir.

The proverb "Time is money" means that "you should not waste time, because you could be using it to earn money; your time does not wait, and you cannot come back and find that time " We translated the proverb "Time is money" word-for-word as "Vaqt pul demakdir" without any change. And also, there is an equivalent proverb: "Vaqting ketti naqting ketti".

Uzbek: "*Vaqting ketti naqting ketti*".

English literary translation: Time is wasted; you lost your point." [author’s translation]

2. Children and fools tell the truth—Bolali uyda gap yotmas.

The English proverb "*Children and fools tell the truth*" means that lying can sometimes be beneficial or advantageous to someone. This is not making a moral claim that lying is good; it simply means that in some circumstances, lying is advantageous for people because the truth can get you into trouble. The only people who don’t know this are children and fools. (<https://writingexplained.org/idiom-dictionary/children-and-fools-tell-the-truth>). A word-for-word Uzbek translation of this proverb is "*bolali uyda gap yotmas*". We considered that some information is missing in translation; for this reason, in our translation, we miss the English word "fools’.

3. Do not count chickens before they are hatched—Jo‘jani kuzda sanaymiz.

There is one equivalent proverb that fits exactly in the Uzbek language. The English proverb "*Do not count chickens before they hatch*" means how many eggs can hatch and how many chickens can survive. Some of them may not hatch due to external damage. We don't know its results or what happens. You should not make plans that depend on something good happening before you know that it has actually happened. A word-for-word Uzbek translation of this proverb is "*jo jani kuzda sanaymiz*". There is kept lexical meaning of proverb but the space-time is changed. In English proverbs, the time expressed is before the eggs hatch, while the time after eggs hatch to become hens is expressed in Uzbek proverbs. There were other equivalents of the proverb: *chuchvarani xom sanama, podadan oldinchang chiqarma*.

Uzbek: "*Chuchvarani xom sanama*"

English literary translation: "Don't count raw dumplings" [author's translation]

Uzbek: "*Podadan oldin chang chiqarma*"

English literary translation: "Don't be dust before the herd" [author's translation]

4. **Fields have eyes, and woods have ears—devorning ham qulog'I bor.**

The proverb "Fields have eyes and woods have ears" means that even though you are outside in an apparently empty landscape, someone may be eavesdropping on you. *Jill: You said you had a secret. Tell me. Jane: Not here. Jill: But there's nobody else in the park. Jane: Fields have eyes, and woods have ears.*"

<https://idioms.thefreedictionary.com/fields+have+eyes%2C+and+woods+have+ears/>.

During our research, we encountered the Uzbek equivalent, *Devorning Ham Qulog'I Bor*. This proverb urges people to be alert and cautious.

5. **There is no such thing as bad weather, only the wrong clothes—Nato'g'ri eshiklar yo'q faqat nato'g'ri kalitlar bor.**

"There's no such thing as bad weather, only bad clothing." What it means is that it's never a bad day to go outside, as long as you're appropriately dressed for the conditions. (Speake Scandinavian). Uzbek people frequently use similar phrases in

this situation, such as *Nato 'g'ri eshiklar yuq faqat nato 'g'ri kalitlar bor*. It means that when you are doing something, you should do it to find the right solution to the problem.

6. Dog does not eat dog. Qarg'a qarg'aning ko'zini cho'qimaydi.

This idiomatic expression means that, in English, one disreputable person will not harm other disreputable people. *Ellen: My lawyer did such a bad job that I want to hire another lawyer to sue him. Jane: You'll never find a lawyer to take on that job. Dog does not eat dog.*

<https://idioms.thefreedictionary.com/dog+does+not+eat+dog>. Uzbek people frequently use similar phrases in this situation, such as *Qarg'a qarg'aning ko'zini cho'qimaydi*. It was translated metaphorically.

CONCLUSION

What justifies the frequent use of some proverbs? They are primarily employed by individuals for inductive objectives, which is the reason. Proverbs and other logical works are unquestionably part of humanity's collective heritage, not just that of a specific nation. Translation and interpretation are important in the transfer of this kind of heritage. We believe that by including our own translations of six English proverbs into Uzbek in this post, we will be able to partially accomplish this mission. The conclusions showed that it is not possible to apply the generalizations "idiomatic expressions are untranslatable" and "words cannot be added or omitted" in all situations. In our instance, we had only one difficulty in translating an English proverb: "fields have eyes, and woods have ears." As a result, we omitted one part of the proverb (*fields have eyes*). Two of the proverbs say, "There is no such thing as bad weather, only the wrong clothes." (*Noto'g'ri eshiklar yo'q faqat*) *Noto'g'ri kalitlar bor*, "Time is money," and *Vaqt pul demakdir* are idiomatic expressions; one of them was translated metaphorically and another was interpreted literally. The success of their familiarity depends on the appropriate context, regardless of how well we succeeded in translating nine English proverbs by taking into account their lexicogrammatical and stylistic aspects. Therefore, in the upcoming studies that are connected, additional researchers will have the chance to talk about this topic.

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